
85. Radial velocities: what wavelength?

GAIA'S THIRD data release, DR3, was issued on 13 June 2022. Alongside more than 1.8 billion stars with their (preliminary) astrometric solutions, it included more than 33 million sources with radial velocities.

To put this in context, when the Hipparcos catalogue of 120 000 stars was released in 1997, radial velocities were known for only some 20 000. High-accuracy radial velocity surveys undertaken by Coravel, amongst others (today often focused on the search for exoplanets) have since measured several thousand more.

Subsequently, and on a larger scale, and in the northern hemisphere between 2005–2010, the Sloan Digital Sky Survey's SEGUE extension obtained spectra of 240 000 stars, with typical radial velocity accuracies of 10 km s^{-1} , with SEGUE-2 observing a further 120 000.

Complementing SEGUE in the southern hemisphere, RAVE (RADial Velocity Experiment) was a multi-fiber spectroscopic survey using the 1.2-metre UK Schmidt Telescope of the Australian Astronomical Observatory and covering 20 000 square degrees, some one half of the sky. Conducted between 2004–2013, and partly motivated by Gaia, RAVE acquired some 574 000 spectra for around 483 000 individual stars.

IN MY ESSAY #8, I summarised the efforts that went into acquiring radial velocities for Hipparcos, and the challenges of obtaining them from the ground.

And I mentioned the main motivation for acquiring radial velocities for as many stars as possible in the first place: viz., to provide the third component of the star's space velocity (given that astrometry can only measure the projected motion of the star across the sky, termed its 'proper motion'). Without it, kinematic and dynamical insights of individual objects – and indeed entire populations – are accordingly greatly restricted.

In preparing for Gaia, it was evident that *multiple* radial velocity measures can also yield information on orbits and orbital companions (whether stars or planets), which themselves can distort knowledge of the star's space motion. But even a single radial velocity measure would provide much valuable information.

WHILE IT WAS desirable to obtain the highest accuracy for all target stars, in practice faint and bright regimes can be loosely distinguished. Faint targets will mostly be distant stars, which will be of interest as tracers of Galactic dynamics. In these cases, the uncertainty in the tangential space motion will be dominated by the parallax error, and a radial velocity accuracy of around 5 km s^{-1} would be adequate for statistical purposes.

Brighter stars, $< 15 \text{ mag}$, will be of more individual interest. Here the radial velocity will be valuable for the determination of perspective acceleration (essay #34), while multiple observations would provide a binarity indicator, also averting errors in the star's space motion.

IN THE FOLLOWING, I will look back to the period leading up to the selection of Gaia in 2000, and recall why the decision was made to acquire radial velocity observations on-board the satellite itself, and the considerations which influenced the choice of spectral range.

THE PARALLEL acquisition of non-astrometric data, both photometric and radial velocity, in the framework of a deep astrometry mission was considered by Perryman (1995). The possibility of acquiring the necessary spectroscopic data (for radial velocities), through dedicated ground-based multi-fibre spectroscopic facilities, was also considered (Bastian 1995). Such programmes were considered as feasible down to magnitudes of 14–15 mag (and indeed helped to catalyse the southern hemisphere RAVE survey), but would nevertheless be logistically complex and very expensive.

There was also a clear scientific return in acquiring *several* radial velocity measurements per star, and doing so not only well spaced in time but, preferably, simultaneously with the astrometric measurements. Given the large number of targets which would be observed, it was not considered practical to acquire such radial velocities from ground-based facilities.

Superior accuracy due to the absence of atmospheric scintillation, and an improved control of systematics, also argued for their acquisition from space.

HAVING MADE the decision to acquire as many radial velocities as possible with Gaia itself, the choice of the spectral region was studied in considerable detail as part of the Gaia Concept and Technology Study (ESA–SCI(2000)4), and in particular in a series of papers by Ulisse Munari from the University of Padua (Munari 1999; Munari & Castelli 2000; Munari et al. 2001). Let me summarise the broad logic driving the eventual choice.

Most Gaia stars are intrinsically red, and made even redder by interstellar absorption. Thus, a red spectral region was to be preferred. To maximise the radial velocity signal even for metal-poor stars, strong, saturated lines are desirable. Broad lines also allow the radial velocity to be accurately derived from moderate-resolution spectra: only a sampling of the lines is needed to derive the radial velocity, while oversampling leads to only marginal improvements in accuracy.

Beyond the $H\alpha$ line at 656.3 nm, three strong spectral features are present in late-type stars: the potassium (K I) doublet near 768 nm, the sodium (Na I) doublet at 819.4 nm, and the calcium (Ca II) triplet near 860 nm.

The K I doublet has only a moderate *equivalent width* ($W = 0.01\text{--}0.04$ nm) and a complicated luminosity dependence. It also is a strong interstellar absorption feature (which complicates its use in the case of strong reddening), and it lies at the core of a strong TiO band, which makes it difficult to use for late spectral types.

The Na I doublet is stronger than the K I doublet, but again has a complex luminosity dependence, for example being weak in giants. Its two lines are also rather close in wavelength (0.16 nm), so that high spectral resolution is required. They are similarly affected by TiO bands. Also, both the K I and the Na I region have no lines in earlier (B and A) stars, so that no radial velocity information can be derived from them in such cases.

THE CA II LINES are strong throughout most of the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, with $W \geq 0.3$ nm for all dwarfs from F8 to M8, and $W \approx 0.6$ nm in supergiants. The lines appear around B8, and dominate in M stars, with a strong luminosity effect. Being non-resonant, there are no problems with contamination by interstellar components. They are strong enough that useful radial velocities can be derived by cross-correlation even in low signal-to-noise spectra. The Ca II lines were duly considered an optimum choice (Munari 1999).

A further advantage of the Ca II infrared triplet region is that, in early-type stars (B, A and early F), where the Ca II lines disappear, the Paschen series of hydrogen appears instead. These lines are also strong, also allow for radial velocity determination, and are also important for classification (Frémat et al. 1996). Finally, the 860 nm spectral region is free from telluric absorption lines, so that follow-up (or complementary) observations from ground can be undertaken in a homogeneous way.

THIS SPECTRAL REGION also contains numerous other features of intrinsic astrophysical interest.

First, the region is not affected by strong molecular bands, but at the same time several metallic lines are present (N I 872.89 nm, Si I 874.26 nm, Mg I 873.60 nm, Ti I 873.47 nm and He I 873.34 nm), which allow for a detailed abundance analysis and quantitative spectral classification for the brighter stars, based on the ratios of equivalent widths.

Second, stars with peculiar spectra are also easily detected in this spectral range. For example, the infrared Ca II spectrum of the proto-typical mass-losing star P Cyg shows a characteristic line-profile prominent in the Paschen and He I lines, and is easily detected even in low signal-to-noise spectra. Classical Be stars are also easily found, as well as classical T Tau stars (which have strong Ca II emission). Active late-type stars generally display emission cores in the Ca II triplet.

Third, while there is no resonant *interstellar* line in the Ca II triplet region, a medium-intensity diffuse interstellar band (DIB) is present at 862 nm. The correlation of its equivalent width with absorption is rather tight, suggesting that it could be used as one of the indicators to build a detailed reddening map, especially for high values of interstellar extinction (Munari 1999).

Example spectra in the Ca II triplet region (0.025 nm per pixel). Left: the effect of temperature from A to M stars; right: the effect of metal abundance in G stars (Munari 1999).

IN FUTURE ESSAYS, I will look more at the implementation of the radial velocity spectrometer on-board Gaia, at the associated data processing, and at the huge range of scientific results that Gaia's radial velocities are enabling today.

While a number of other scientists picked up the huge challenge of optimising the Gaia radial velocity instrument, and addressing the complexities of the data analysis, I wanted to revisit here the early foundations on which the implementation was based. Although Ulisse Munari moved on to other activities, I wanted to credit the key role he played in suggesting and quantifying this important direction for Gaia.